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Leveraging LLMs for Smart Cities Qualitative Data Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Public authorities frequently conduct surveys and analyze data from citizens, a process that is often labor-intensive when performed manually. This paper explores how generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) can assist in automating data analysis for public authorities. In this respect, we investigate the potential of large language models (LLMs) to perform sentiment analysis and summarization of unstructured data as smart services. Using data from the East Bristol livable neighborhood (EBLN) as a case study, we assess the accuracy and precision of these models and validate the results against ground truth data and expert evaluations. Our findings indicate that sentiment classification achieved over 90% accuracy. Additionally, incorporating retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) further enhances the results obtained. Comparative analysis revealed that LLMs achieved superior performance over traditional summarization techniques based on domain expert evaluation. These results suggest that LLMs offer a promising and impactful approach to improving the efficiency of qualitative analysis, though further research is required to enhance their accuracy and usefulness.

1 | Introduction

Cities are undergoing significant transformations as they seek to harness the full potential of urban governance driven by Information and Communication Technology [1]. Several benefits are sought to manage the complexity of urban systems and gain insights from public participation in planning processes [2, 3]. An important driving force in this transformation concerns the information overload from urban systems and local initiatives such as citizen observatories. The recent policy shift toward more emphasis on citizen engagement in data gathering, planning, and decision-making processes, for example, European Bauhaus,¹ Built4People² and EU Mission Cities,³ requires further technological support to manage and analyze such datasets. In particular, much of the data is gathered through surveys or comments provided by citizens on specific plans or topics via social media or other participation platforms. Since these datasets are

typically unstructured, analyzing them can be time-consuming and requires specific skills. This problem can be exacerbated by the growing number of surveys and the high levels of public participation.

During the past decade, data analytics has emerged as an important innovative technology in the domain of smart cities [4, 5]. Various statistical, machine learning, and data mining techniques have proven to be revolutionary in the context of Smart City Data Analytics. Among these, deep learning models have become one of the most cutting-edge technologies, offering significant contributions across a range of applications for smart city services [6, 7].

Recently, disruptive technologies such as generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) and large language models (LLMs) are revolutionizing the way data analysis can be performed. Their

Abbreviations: EBLN, East Bristol livable neighborhood; LLM, large language model; RAG, retrieval-augmented generation.

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benefits span domains such as transportation planning, urban planning, and smart buildings. Their ability to analyze and evaluate unstructured qualitative data with high accuracy and precision makes them ideal candidates to help public authorities streamline their processes. In this respect, we investigate the suitability of LLMs for two automated services for public authorities: (i) sentiment analysis and (ii) summarization of survey data. We applied selected models to real, unstructured textual data collected through the East Bristol livable neighborhood (EBLN)⁴ initiative in Bristol, United Kingdom. Monitoring the impact of the EBLN is one of the pilots under the Horizon Europe GREENGAGE project.⁵ The GREENGAGE project aims to develop citizen observatories to facilitate European GREEN Deal policy objectives across different pilots in the EU and the UK. By leveraging citizen science, the project aims to collect extensive unstructured qualitative data through surveys, discussions (audio), and comments gathered through the GREENGAGE GREEN Engine, such as mobile apps. Additionally, the project will combine sensor data from traffic monitoring and pollution levels, with citizens' feedback to raise public awareness and engagement in environmental issues, as well as to gather their opinions and needs on these topics.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents background information on LLMs and their suitability for data analysis tasks. Section 3 introduces the EBLN dataset, detailing our preprocessing steps, model architectures, and experimental design of the two key services: sentiment analysis and text summarization. We discuss our findings and their implications in Section 4, followed by conclusive remarks in Section 5.

2 | Background

2.1 | Large Language Models for Qualitative Analytics

Traditional approaches to qualitative data analysis rely on understanding vast amounts of unstructured data (text, video, or audio) through manual processes [8]. These approaches typically require significant time investments and are heavily dependent on human expertise, inevitably incorporating individual biases into the analytical process.

The rise of LLMs has encouraged a shift toward developing more sophisticated, automated systems for qualitative data analysis. These models, comprising billions of parameters and trained on vast datasets, have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in various language processing tasks [9]. Several studies have explored the application of LLMs in qualitative analysis, focusing on either specific tasks such as sentiment analysis [10], text summarization [11, 12], theory-driven categorization [13], or holistic solutions [14, 15]. However, there remains a gap in understanding their practical benefits in real-world scenarios. Current research often lacks evaluation from end-users or applications in real smart cities case studies. This study aims to address this gap by applying LLMs to recent survey data and incorporating feedback from actual practitioners. Our final goal is to set the foundation for future research directions and assess the true potential of LLMs in qualitative data analysis within practical contexts.

2.2 | Zero-Shot Learning and LLMs

Training machine learning models is a resource-intensive task, requiring substantial data, time, and computational power [16]. However, real-world scenarios often impose limitations on these resources. Zero-shot learning is a machine learning paradigm that enables models to make predictions for classes they have not encountered during training [17], reducing computational costs and the need for large amounts of annotated datasets. While this has been mainly used for computer vision, it has recently gained attraction with the surge of LLMs [18].

LLMs are pretrained on vast amounts of data, capable of performing a wide range of language tasks effectively. Zero-shot learning leverages this extensive knowledge base, making LLMs flexible and adaptable across various scenarios. Given the ability of LLMs to understand and generate human-like text, LLMs can be directed to perform zero-shot learning simply through natural language instructions or 'prompts' [19]. This conversational manner of task description allows these models to adapt to new contexts without the need for task-specific training data, time-consuming data preparation steps, or extensive model fine-tuning. Moreover, this approach is particularly beneficial in providing nonexperts with a tool to perform language analysis.

In this study, we have created suitable prompts to perform zero-shot learning for sentiment classification and summarization. Creating effective prompts involves a trial-and-error approach, which can be challenging [20]. While exploring the nuances of prompt creation is outside the scope of this initial study, we will focus on discussing the results obtained. It is important to note that varying prompts may yield different results in this context.

2.3 | Retrieval-Augmented Generation

LLMs are constrained by the data they were trained on, which can become outdated or insufficient for specific queries. This limitation affects the models' *context awareness*, or their ability to generate accurate and relevant responses, particularly in dynamic or specialized domains [21]. Recently, the retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) technique has been implemented to enhance the capabilities of LLMs [22]. Instead of relying solely on the static knowledge embedded in the model, RAG dynamically retrieves relevant information from external sources, such as databases, documents, or the web. This retrieved information, similar to the data that needs to be classified or analyzed, augments the initial LLM input, resulting in more accurate and contextually appropriate response generation. RAG has demonstrated to improve the accuracy of responses in various contexts [23], and to be a cost-effective solution, as it eliminates the need to retrain the model with new or specific data, leveraging existing knowledge bases instead [24].

2.4 | Sentiment Classification Using LLMs

Understanding public opinion, citizens' experiences and satisfaction is crucial in the context of Smart Cities. This enables

authorities to assess initiative reception, pinpoint concerns, improve quality of life, and ensure responsive governance. To accomplish these objectives effectively, sentiment classification emerges as an invaluable analytical tool [25]. This natural language processing technique aims to determine the emotional tone or attitude expressed in a piece of text. It typically involves categorizing text into binary sentiments—positive or negative—although more nuanced classifications are also feasible.

Traditional sentiment classification techniques often rely on lexicon-based methods, which use predefined dictionaries of sentiment-bearing words, or machine learning approaches such as Naive Bayes, support vector machines, and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), which learn from labeled data [26]. These techniques, while effective, can struggle with context-dependent sentiments, require large amounts of labeled data for training, and demand extensive feature engineering and dataset preparation, which can be time-consuming and costly to perform. In contrast, LLMs excel in understanding context and nuanced language, require minimal task-specific training due to their pre-trained nature, and can perform well with limited or no labeled data [10, 26]. LLMs' versatility in processing sentiments across a range of domains, with superior accuracy, makes them ideal for sentiment analysis, especially in the context of survey data collection, characterized by large quantitative of unstructured data covering different topics.

2.5 | Summarization Using LLMs

In the digital age, where information is abundant and readily available, the ability to condense and summarize text is of high importance. Text summarization serves as a powerful tool that aids in the efficient extraction and comprehension of key information from large volumes of data. It enables individuals and businesses to sift through vast amounts of content and quickly identify the most relevant and critical information. By transforming lengthy documents into concise summaries, it saves time, enhances productivity, and supports informed decision-making processes. As such, text summarization plays a crucial role in navigating information overload in today's data-driven world.

Text summarization approaches have been around for a while. For example, frequency-based, graph-based, and topic-based approaches aid in extractive summarization techniques. On the other hand, Sequence-to-Sequence models such as RNNs and LSTMs aid abstractive summarization. The emergence of LLMs promises to usher in a new era of summarization techniques. However, being relatively recent, not much work has been performed to investigate the performance of LLMs for summarization in various domains. Although there is limited research, it suggests that traditional approaches still perform reasonably well for generic tasks, though LLMs might outperform them when fine-tuned for specific domains [27, 28]. Therefore, in this paper, we explore how LLMs perform in the summarization of survey data.

3 | Material and Methods

3.1 | Case Study and Data Collection

The EBLN project is a community-driven initiative to transform East Bristol's streets. The main goal is to collaborate with local residents, workers, students, and commuters to design streets that are livable and people-friendly. This project is part of a co-design phase aimed at developing long-term solutions with the help of the local community. Monitoring the EBLN is also a pilot in the Horizon Europe GREENGAGE project, which promotes inclusive citizen observatories by using digital solutions.

The survey data used in this study were collected between January and March 2022 by Bristol City Council, UK. Participants, including those living, working, or traveling to the area, shared their opinions either using an interactive online map,⁶ or by engaging with members of Bristol City Council through door-to-door interviews or community discussions.

Face-to-face interviews were conducted and recorded manually. Citizens were asked about their thoughts on what they appreciate about their local area, and how they would like to improve it. They had the option to respond to either or both questions, resulting in over 400 individual contributions and a total of 845 comments of varying length. While the complete dataset cannot be disclosed due to confidentiality constraints, Table 1 presents a representative sample of responses collected.

Using the online tool instead, citizens could express their feedback by:

- Marking specific locations on a map
- Linking a feeling, chosen from a range of five sentiments, spanning from negative to positive, with the selected area
- Providing optional comments in a free-text box
- Additionally, selecting one or more topics related to their comments, reasons for their expressed feeling, and suggestions for improving the area

TABLE 1 | Example of responses from the EBLN interviews.

Q1: What do you like about your local area?
A1: Good sense of community
A2: It's fairly diverse – there's a real sense of community, it feels very friendly
A3: Park, shops
Q2: How would you like to make it better?
A4: More activities for children and improve parks. Homes are too old and damaged and we need repairs
A5: Traffic
A6: Wider roads

TABLE 2 | Example of responses from the online EBLN map.

Category	Response details
Sentiment: Positive	
Subjects	Trees and greenery on street, Street trees and planting
Reasons	Pleasant
Suggestions	Slow down traffic
Comments	The street planters have reduced traffic speed and made the street 'greener'. Something similar could be done in other locations within the project area and in traffic displacement areas outside the project area
Sentiment: Negative	
Subjects	Walking, Crossings
Reasons	Not pedestrian friendly, Difficult to cross the street
Suggestion	Add crossing, Safer junction for walking and cycling
Comments	Hard to cross here— there is a traffic island slightly above this point but often want to cross lower down and it's hard to do so as the road is busy with two lanes of fast traffic.

An example of responses from the online survey is shown in Table 2.

The dataset collected through the online tool comprises 540 geo-located entries, of which ~90% contain both textual comments and sentiment labels. A preliminary study conducted on this dataset [29], which involved analyzing the textual comments alongside the provided sentiment and topic labels, showed that most participants lived within the area and tended to emphasize negative aspects of their neighborhood, particularly in relation to main roads and junctions. Interestingly, the word 'road' frequently appeared in negative contexts, while 'street' was associated with positive sentiments, reflecting nuanced perceptions of different urban spaces. Conversely, areas with green spaces generally received more positive feedback. Sentiment analysis showed that negative statements were more prevalent around safety and environment-related comments, while texts linked to community aspects displayed a more balanced distribution of sentiments.

The preliminary study [29] demonstrated the potential of analyzing public feedback to inform urban planning initiatives. However, it also highlights the need for scalable and efficient methodologies. While the EBLN dataset has labeled textual data, most urban datasets lack such structured annotations, resulting in the need for extensive time to analyze and generate comprehensive summaries to extract insights and actionable steps.

In this study, we have tested our LLM-based methods against the EBLN datasets. For sentiment classification, we have focused on the online EBLN dataset, leveraging its preexisting sentiment

labels to assess our approach's accuracy and effectiveness. For the summarization tasks, we have worked with both the online and in-person collected data, and results have been evaluated by members of Bristol City Council directly involved in the EBLN and GREENGAGE project.

3.2 | Data Preprocessing

Our work centers exclusively on the free-text comments and their corresponding sentiment labels in the case of the sentiment classification task, therefore all other features in our datasets were excluded. In line with our aim of utilizing LLMs, our preprocessing was intentionally minimal. This is because LLMs are designed to handle natural language inputs, including variations in spelling, grammar, and informal expressions commonly found in public feedback. Therefore, for both tasks, we retained all comments regardless of length to preserve the full range of citizen feedback, since even brief comments can provide insight into urban perceptions.

For the summarization tasks, two files were generated that included all the text comments. These comments were either placed in one column for the online dataset or in two columns for the two questions asked during the interviews. In the case of the sentiment classification task, we tested the model with different setups. The original dataset included five sentiment categories: positive, mostly positive, neutral, mostly negative, and negative. We first performed a sentiment simplification: following the approach in [29], we have excluded the neutral comments, and grouped the remaining labels into two polar groups, positive and negative. This allowed us to perform a binary classification to facilitate a clearer, more straightforward interpretation of public opinions, and avoid the complexities of neutral or fine-grained sentiment analysis. Next, we evaluated the models with ternary sentiments (positive, neutral, and negative) and the original five-category classification. This was done to evaluate the model's performance across different levels of sentiment granularity and to understand how well the model can handle varying degrees of sentiment complexity. As a result of our preprocessing, our method was tested for the binary classification on 446 textual comments from the EBLN survey, with 52 comments labeled as positive. In the other two scenarios, which included neutral comments, we used 507 comments. Specifically, for the five-category classification, we used the original comment distribution: 272 comments were categorized as negative, 122 as mostly negative, 41 as positive, and 11 as mostly positive.

3.3 | Service 1: Sentiment Classification

For the sentiment classification task in this study, we have tested the Flan-T5 language model, developed by Google AI in 2022 [30]. Flan-T5 is an open-source, improved version of the original T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer) [31] model, treating all natural language processing tasks as text-to-text problems. This model has been fine-tuned on a diverse range of tasks using instruction-based learning, making it suitable to be used in a zero-shot learning context. This versatile approach adapts well to sentiment classification, with the model's instruction-following ability making it an easy tool for language analysis, even for

nontechnical users. Flan-T5 is comparable in performance to many heavyweight, proprietary models while being open-source [32], reducing cost constraints and allowing customization. These features make it an excellent candidate for our investigation, balancing advanced capabilities, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness.

Google has released multiple variants of Flan-T5, ranging from compact models with 80 million parameters and 300MB in size to expansive versions with 11 billion parameters requiring 80GB of memory. For this study, we evaluated the following checkpoints available on Hugging Face:⁷

- Flan-T5-small: 80 million parameters, 300 MB
- Flan-T5-base: 250 million parameters, 990 MB
- Flan-T5-large: 780 million parameters, 1 GB

The choice of these model sizes was motivated by the aim to assess the performance on common laptops with limited resources, evaluate the trade-off between execution time and accuracy across different model sizes, and make the approach accessible to a wide range of users.

Given the zero-shot learning strategy adopted in this study, hyperparameter tuning was intentionally avoided to preserve the model's pretrained instruction-following behavior and to ensure reproducible and deterministic outputs. Therefore, temperature remains at the default value of 1.0, the input prompt length is kept fixed at 512 tokens, and beam search is configured at 1 (single path), resulting in greedy decoding where the model selects the most probable token at each step.

To provide a comprehensive comparison, we tested these models both on a laptop device with an Intel Core i5 processor and on an NVIDIA Titan RTX GPU-equipped computer. This additional test helped us quantify the reduction in execution time achievable with more powerful hardware, providing insights into the scalability of our approach.

All the Flan-T5 model variants mentioned were tested using identical prompt instructions to ensure a consistent and fair

comparison across different model sizes. We aimed to use a clear and straightforward prompt, including only the essential components, namely the task name, task definition, and output format (Listing 1). Prompt format and wording were taken from the work of Zhang et al. [32].

LISTING 1: Prompt for sentiment classification task.

```
Please perform sentiment classification task.
Given the sentence, assign a sentiment label
from {labels}.
Return label only.
Sentence: {text}
Label:
```

In the prompt above, we specify the name of the task (Sentiment Classification) and provide instructions on the task itself (assign a label to a given sentence). We also specify the output format we require after the final word 'Label'. The {labels} placeholder is substituted with the allowed labels for the three tested scenarios. For example, in the ternary sentiment classification, the labels are [positive, negative, neutral]. We have executed this prompt for every data point in the dataset, replacing {text} with the appropriate comment sentence from the dataset.

Despite testing multiple prompt formulations, we observed only marginal differences in model performance. This finding aligns with existing literature [32], which indicates that for tasks such as sentiment classification, the specific wording of prompts tends to have a limited influence on the overall performance of LLMs. Consequently, we report results using the standard prompt described above, as it is representative and sufficiently effective for the task, while also ensuring consistency across model comparisons.

3.3.1 | Sentiment Classification With RAG

Figure 1 illustrates the RAG system implemented in this study. After survey responses are loaded, embeddings for each comment are generated using the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 model,⁸ a sentence-transformer optimized for tasks requiring sentence similarity searches. This embedding process enhances and accelerates similarity searches with other texts in the external

FIGURE 1 | Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) workflow implemented for the sentiment analysis.

knowledge base dataset. The same embedding process is applied to the knowledge base dataset.

The RAG system implementation comprises three stages:

1. **Retrieval:** This stage compares the vector embeddings of input EBLN responses against the knowledge base embeddings. We employ *cosine similarity* as our similarity metric because it effectively captures semantic relationships between vector embeddings, while being computationally efficient and scale-invariant. The system implements a top-5 retrieval approach, selecting the five most relevant comments and their respective labels from our knowledge base that match each input query.
2. **Context Augmentation:** The retrieved context enriches the original input by incorporating the most relevant examples from the knowledge base. This augmentation provides the model with additional context and similar examples to inform its classification decision. The specific prompt template used is described in Listing 2. We replace {examples} with the top 5 similar answers from the retrieval stages, presented in the form of “Sentence: <retrieved example> Label: <corresponding label>”.
3. **Response Generation:** The final stage produces a classification label based on the augmented prompt. These generated labels are stored and subsequently compared against the original EBLN labels for evaluation purposes.

LISTING 2: Augmented prompt for sentiment classification task.

```
Please perform sentiment classification task.
Given the sentence, assign a sentiment label
from {labels}.
Return label only.
{examples}
Sentence: {text}
Label:
```

In our implementation, the RAG system functions as a dynamic few-shot learning approach, where the top-5 retrieved examples serve as case-specific demonstrations for each input. Unlike traditional few-shot learning, which uses fixed examples [33], our system selectively includes the most relevant cases from the knowledge base in each prompt. This approach applies the principle of context engineering [34] by dynamically selecting contextually appropriate examples while maintaining efficient prompt lengths, allowing the model to access specialized guidance for each classification decision.

The RAG system implemented incorporates the SentiHood dataset [35] as its external knowledge base. This dataset contains opinions about London neighborhoods, with sentences labeled with binary sentiments (positive/negative) associated with specific aspects of different locations. We performed minimal preprocessing by removing entries without labels and resolving multiple labels per sentence by selecting the most frequent one, resulting in 3056 labeled sentences. To adapt the SentiHood dataset for use in the RAG system with 3 and 5 sentiment classes, we performed a relabeling procedure to expand the label set accordingly. For this approach, we have used the Google Gemini 2.5 Pro model,⁹ chosen for its strong generalization capabilities. The

use of a model external to the RAG architecture was a deliberate design choice intended to mitigate bias inheritance [36]: employing the same model for both the relabeling and the generation stage risks amplifying shared inductive biases, potentially skewing sentiment prediction toward dominant patterns. To ensure the quality and the semantic consistency of the relabeling process, a series of validation checks was performed following label generation. Specifically, we aimed to verify that the expanded multiclass labels remained aligned with the original binary annotations. For example, comments originally labeled as ‘positive’ in the binary scheme were expected to map only to ‘positive’ or ‘neutral’ in a three-class setting. Similarly, a ‘neutral’ label in the ternary setup was expected to remain ‘neutral’ in the five-class version, whereas a ‘positive’ label could be reasonably extended to ‘mostly positive’ or ‘positive’. Labels that failed to meet these consistency criteria were manually reviewed and adjusted to ensure alignment with the original sentiment intent. To further validate the quality of the knowledge base relabeling, a representative 10% sample was assessed by the authors to confirm the contextual reliability of the expanded label set for use within the RAG framework.

3.4 | Service 2: Text Summarization

To evaluate the summarization service, we conducted a comparative analysis between LLMs and traditional summarization techniques. The traditional methods encompassed both *extractive* and *abstractive* approaches [37, 38]. For extractive summarization, we selected latent semantic analysis (LSA) [39] and LexRank [40]. For abstractive summarization, we employed BART-Large [41] and Pegasus [42], both fine-tuned on the CNN/Daily Mail dataset [43], along with T5 [31]. For LLM-based summarization, we evaluated LLaMA 3.1 8B [44] and Mistral 7B Instruct [45]. The selection of models was guided by a balance between state-of-the-art performance and practical feasibility on consumer-grade hardware. Consequently, we focused on smaller-scale LLMs that remain practical for researchers and practitioners with limited computational resources. The evaluation was conducted on a workstation with an NVIDIA Titan RTX GPU; however, the selected models’ modest size ensures reproducibility on similar or less powerful hardware.

For extractive summarization, we employed the sumy library¹⁰ (v0.11.0). Abstractive models were implemented using the Hugging Face transformers library.¹¹ LLMs were deployed via the ollama framework¹² (v0.9.0) with the langchain-community client¹³ (v0.4). To ensure consistency across models, we adopted a set of standard hyperparameters: the temperature was set to 0.7 to balance diversity and coherence in the generated summaries; the output token limit was capped at 128 to promote conciseness; and a context window of 16,384 tokens was used to accommodate longer input sequences while maintaining computational efficiency.

For traditional summarization techniques, which typically do not support large context windows, we implemented a chunking strategy to process long texts. This approach is formalized in Algorithm 1, which recursively divides the input text into manageable segments and summarizes each individually.

ALGORITHM 1 | Recursive text summarization algorithm.

Require: Input text T , summarizer S , tokenizer K , maximum input length L_{\max} , summary length bounds $(L_{\min}, L_{\max_summary})$, chunk summary bounds (C_{\min}, C_{\max})

Ensure: Summary of T

```

1: if length( $K.encode(T)$ )  $\leq L_{\max}$  then
2:   if word_count( $T$ )  $< L_{\min}$  then
3:     return  $T$ 
4:   else
5:      $summary \leftarrow S(T, \text{max\_length} = L_{\max\_summary}, \text{min\_length} = L_{\min}, \text{do\_sample} = \text{False})$ 
6:     return  $summary[0][\text{esummary\_text}\epsilon]$ 
7:   end if
8: else
9:    $chunks \leftarrow \text{ChunkTextBySentences}(T, K, L_{\max})$ 
10:   $chunk\_summaries \leftarrow []$ 
11:  for each  $chunk$  in  $chunks$  do
12:    if word_count( $chunk$ )  $< C_{\min}$  then
13:      Append  $chunk$  to  $chunk\_summaries$ 
14:    else
15:       $chunk\_summary \leftarrow S(chunk, \text{max\_length} = C_{\max}, \text{min\_length} = C_{\min}, \text{do\_sample} = \text{False})$ 
16:      Append  $chunk\_summary[0][\text{esummary\_text}\epsilon]$  to  $chunk\_summaries$ 
17:    end if
18:  end for
19:   $combined\_summary \leftarrow \text{Join}(chunk\_summaries)$ 
20:  return GENERALSUMMARISE( $combined\_summary, S, K, L_{\max}, (L_{\min}, L_{\max\_summary}), (C_{\min}, C_{\max})$ )
21: END IF

```

The algorithm accepts a text input T , a summarizer function S , and a tokenizer K , along with configurable parameters: maximum input length (L_{\max}), summary length bounds ($L_{\min}, L_{\max_summary}$), and chunk summary bounds (C_{\min}, C_{\max}). If the tokenized input length is within L_{\max} , the algorithm checks whether the text is too short to summarize meaningfully (i.e., below L_{\min} words). If so, the original text is returned; otherwise, the summarizer S is applied directly to produce a summary within the specified bounds. For longer inputs, the text is segmented using a sentence-aware chunking function that ensures each chunk respects the L_{\max} constraint. Each chunk is then summarized individually unless it is too short, in which case it is retained as-is. The resulting chunk summaries are concatenated and passed recursively back into the algorithm until the final summary conforms to the input constraints. This recursive strategy ensures scalability and robustness for summarizing arbitrarily long texts, while maintaining control over output length and semantic coherence.

We also employed prompt engineering techniques to fine-tune the prompt used to instruct the LLMs to summarize the responses. Based on incremental testing [46], the prompt shown in Listing 3 was finalized.

LISTING 3: System prompt for the summarization task.

```

<instructions>
You are an expert AI assistant tasked with
  summarizing survey responses.

Your goal is to create a clear, concise, and
  detailed summary of the provided text.

If provided, prioritize addressing the following
  context in the summary:

```

```

<context>
{context}
</context>

Here is the content from the survey:
<survey>
{text}
</survey>
</instructions>

FINAL SUMMARY:
<summary>
</summary>

```

For each prompt, 9 different contexts were devised. These contexts could also include instructions for the LLMs to tailor the summary that was generated. For example, it could include instructions to “focus only on transport related responses” or “what do citizens say about bus services?”. Therefore, including no context, there were 10 total summaries generated for each LLM (Table 3). The summaries were then ranked by domain experts as to their usefulness from 1 to 5, 1 being least useful and 5 being most useful. Two domain experts from Bristol City Council were recruited, and they were instructed to provide a single score for each response. No specific instructions were provided to the experts regarding the usefulness of the responses, as it was thought best to leave the interpretation up to them. They were, however, asked to provide comments on the scores, which helped us understand their thought process and subsequently analyze and interpret the scores. The results are discussed in Section 4.2. A *streamlit*¹⁴ webapp (Figure 2) was created to allow different users to experiment with providing various contexts.

4 | Results and Discussion

4.1 | Sentiment Analysis

In our evaluation of the Flan-T5 models, we focused on two key classification metrics, accuracy and F1-score, since they respectively provide an overview of the overall correctness and the balance between precision and recall. For the multiclass

TABLE 3 | Contexts supplied by domain experts.

ID	Context
1	No context
2	What do people think about bus services
3	What do people think about cycle lanes
4	Tell me about bike storage in the area
5	What do people like about their area
6	Tell me about green spaces
7	Tell me about air quality
8	What do people think about traffic
9	What do people think about anti-social behavior
10	What is the biggest issue in the area

classification scenarios, we used a weighted F1-score to account for the varying number of occurrences in each class, given the dataset's imbalance.

4.1.1 | Zero-Shot Classification

For the binary classification scenario, the performance of our approach is reported in Table 4. The accuracy results demonstrate a clear progression as model size increases. The Flan-T5-large model performs significantly better, with 92% of its predictions being correct, and there is a notable jump in accuracy from the base to the large model, in line with the increase in model parameters. The F1 scores follow a similar trend, with all

TABLE 4 | Binary Classification: performance metrics for different Flan-T5 models.

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	Time (CPU)	Time (GPU)
Flan-T5-small	0.81	0.88	1 min 43 s	20 s
Flan-T5-base	0.85	0.91	4 min 49 s	50 s
Flan-T5-large	0.92	0.95	14 min 15 s	2 min 25 s

Summary Generator

Provide any context you wish to. This is optional:

Focus on transportation related issues.

Provide a comments in an .xlsx file to summarise:

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file • XLSX

Browse files

comment.xlsx 29.6KB

Submit

Successfully generated the following summary.

Here is a detailed summary of the transportation-related issues discussed by what appears to be residents of Barton Hill area:

Public Transportation:

- Many residents rely on buses to get to school or work, but they are dissatisfied with the current service, citing delays and unreliability.
- There is a need for more frequent and reliable bus services, particularly along Church Road.

FIGURE 2 | A Streamlit webapp created to experiment with different contexts.

models showing high scores, hence a good balance between false positives and false negatives errors made.

In terms of computational efficiency, we evaluated the model's execution time on both CPU and GPU configurations. Running Flan-T5 with GPU acceleration results in roughly an 80% reduction in processing time compared to CPU execution. However, it is worth noticing that even with the larger model requiring > 14 min for processing, this is still substantially faster than the time an analyst would spend classifying such data manually, which, according to staff members at Bristol City Council, could range from a couple of hours to days depending on the complexity and volume of the data. For Flan-T5-large, by analyzing the errors obtained, we see in particular that only one positive instance gets predicted as negative, and we have 34 false positives. Looking at these errors, we can notice that they occur mostly on statements that are not fully negative or positive in the sentiment spectrum, or where mixed feelings are present in the same statement. Table 5 shows some examples of these errors, where 'True' corresponds to the label selected by the respondent and simplified to binary form during our data preprocessing phase.

Overall, these results are quite positive. The consistent improvement in both metrics as model size increases suggests that larger models do indeed capture more nuanced patterns in the data, leading to better classification performance. However, this comes at the cost of increased execution time. Despite this, the computational time remains significantly lower than what would be required for manual analysis, demonstrating the efficiency of automated approaches even with larger models.

The performance of Flan-T5 models for multiclass sentiment classification is presented in Table 6. In this part of the study, the models were tested exclusively on a CPU, and no comparison with GPU performance was conducted, as the primary objective was to understand how well the model performs across different sentiment granularities. The overall accuracy observed is lower compared to binary classification. This discrepancy may be attributed to the model's requirement to discern between closely related classes, particularly the ambiguous 'neutral' class and fine-grained distinctions such as 'mostly positive' versus 'positive', which poses significant challenges due to the inherent complexity of the task and the larger decision boundary [32]. Such subtleties are difficult to capture effectively without targeted training, and may also be influenced by the intricacies of prompt engineering [47], and by the model's pretraining on large,

uncurated internet data, which often includes inconsistent or atypical sentiment expressions [48].

Consistent with binary classification, model performance scales positively with size in three-class sentiment classification. However, the confusion matrices in Figure 3 reveal a persistent challenge across all model sizes: Systematic struggles with neutral class prediction. Smaller models demonstrate pronounced conflation of negative and neutral sentiments, while larger models achieve improved class separation. This observation aligns with established research demonstrating that classification methods typically struggle with the neutral class, as neutral texts often lie near the decision boundaries of binary classifiers, creating inherent classification ambiguity [10, 49].

However, the positive scaling relationship reverses in five-class sentiment classification, where larger models paradoxically exhibit degraded performance. Such an outcome can be attributed to the increased number of parameters, which makes larger models more prone to overfitting on instruction data and amplifying dataset noise. These observations align with recent findings that 'overparameterized' models might struggle with complex tasks [50, 51], while smaller models can outperform larger ones in tasks that demand fine-grained discrimination [32]. In zero-shot scenarios, this translates into larger models often exhibiting overconfidence, relying on coarse pretrained associations ill-suited for subtle sentiment gradations. Such behavior highlights the need for improved training strategies to better encode emotional subtlety [52]. As shown in Figure 4,

TABLE 6 | Multiclass classification performance metrics compared to binary classification results.

Models	No. classes	Accuracy	F1-score
Flan-T5-small	2	0.81	0.88
	3	0.51	0.56
	5	0.38	0.36
Flan-T5-base	2	0.85	0.91
	3	0.65	0.68
	5	0.30	0.35
Flan-T5-large	2	0.92	0.95
	3	0.77	0.78
	5	0.23	0.14

TABLE 5 | Binary classification: some false positives and false negatives results from Flan-T5-large.

Statement	True	Predicted
There should be trees planted at this junction, there is plenty of space on the central island and wide footway. This would make the area look more pleasant and less industrial. They would also help absorb pollution.	Negative	Positive
Perfect place for diagonal pedestrian crossing please please please?! I can think of no better place for this in Bristol. So many stages to crossing this street. Phasing of lights should favor pedestrians and cyclists not cars.	Negative	Positive
The public rights of way on Troopers Hill need diverting to follow the existing paths, at the moment OS and other maps show routes that cannot be followed.	Positive	Negative

FIGURE 3 | Confusion matrices for FLAN-T5 models in three-classes sentiment classification.

FIGURE 4 | Confusion matrices for FLAN-T5 models in five-classes sentiment classification.

TABLE 7 | Multiclass classification: some misclassified examples from Flan-T5-large.

Statement	True	Predicted
The river and the surrounding area are badly affected by fly tipping and general litter.	Negative	Mostly Negative
Make one-way roads in opposing directions to stop rat running	Mostly Negative	Neutral
This path is good and really well used, but after dark it's scary and dangerous as there is no lighting	Neutral	Mostly Negative
Pleasant street to walk and run down with greenery and fewer cars	Mostly Positive	Positive
Wonderful path away from motor vehicle traffic. Slightly wider and lighting at night would make it even better	Positive	Mostly Positive

confusion matrices reveal a systematic collapse of class boundaries, with frequent conflation of sentiment intensity within the same polarity. Similar to the three-class results, neutral predictions are dispersed across classes. Notably, smaller models show concentrated errors, while larger models show more distributed confusion, suggesting that increased capacity leads to more systematic but incorrect pattern recognition rather than better discrimination. Table 7 shows some examples of these misclassifications, where ‘True’ corresponds to the label selected by the respondent at the time of the survey. These cases illustrate the inherent challenges of sentiment analysis, particularly with mixed or context-dependent language. In the first example, the model predicts ‘Mostly Negative’ instead of ‘Negative’, likely due

to the descriptive tone lacking strong emotional cues. In the second case, a suggestion to reduce ‘rat running’ is interpreted as ‘Neutral’, possibly because the model overlooks the implied negative sentiment without broader context. The third example demonstrates a shift from positive to negative sentiment within a single sentence. The model emphasizes the latter, whereas the respondent labeled it ‘Neutral’, perhaps balancing both sentiments. In the last two examples, the model’s predictions align broadly with the respondent’s sentiment but do not match precisely. These discrepancies suggest that human perceptions of sentiment, especially neutrality, can be subjective, indicating that models may sometimes apply more consistent or logically weighted judgments than human annotators.

These results indicate that we need more nuance in our approach, perhaps by analyzing sentiments at the sentence level or on different topics within each statement, rather than assigning a single sentiment to the full statement. Such an approach could better capture the complexity and potential ambiguity in responses, particularly those containing multiple, not binary, or conflicting sentiments.

4.1.2 | RAG-Based Classification

This part of the study was conducted exclusively on a CPU to solely evaluate the efficacy of retrieval-augmented LLMs. The results of the binary RAG-based classification are presented in Table 8.

Notably, the inference execution time did not increase significantly. The performance pattern mirrors the binary classification results, where larger models consistently outperform smaller

TABLE 8 | Performance Comparison of Flan-T5 Models with and without RAG Integration for binary classification.

Models	Metric	With RAG	Without RAG
Flan-T5-small	Accuracy	0.88	0.81
	F1-Score	0.91	0.88
	Time (CPU)	2 min 17 s	1 min 43 s
Flan-T5-base	Accuracy	0.87	0.85
	F1-Score	0.93	0.91
	Time (CPU)	6 min 15 s	4 min 49 s
Flan-T5-large	Accuracy	0.95	0.92
	F1-Score	0.97	0.95
	Time (CPU)	19 min 37 s	14 min 15 s

ones. The integration of an external knowledge base through the RAG system improves the results, demonstrating the potential of retrieval-augmented approaches in sentiment analysis tasks. Table 9 presents several retrieved examples for specific inputs, along with the labels predicted by the Flan-T5-large model.

Tables 10 and 11 summarize the results of the RAG-based sentiment classification for the 3 and 5-class settings, respectively. In the binary setting, RAG consistently improved accuracy across all model sizes (Table 8), suggesting that retrieval helps reinforce clear-cut sentiment distinction. However, in the 3 and 5-class setting, the impact of RAG varied: while Flan-T5 Large showed a modest improvement, Flan-T5 Small experienced a performance drop. This discrepancy may stem from the increased complexity of multiclass classification, where retrieved examples introduce additional ambiguity that smaller models struggle to resolve [32]. The modest performance of RAG may also be influenced by the type of knowledge base and its relevance to the input and tasks at hand [22], both of which influence the quality of retrieved examples and the model's ability to generalize across nuanced sentiment distinctions. The SentiHood knowledge base, while thematically relevant for urban opinion analysis, presents two significant constraints that can introduce biases and inaccuracies: its small size and geographic specificity to London. These constraints limit the diversity of examples available for retrieval and may hinder the generalization of sentiment patterns to other cities. Since linguistic expressions and sentiment cues often vary across regions, a London-centric dataset may encode location-specific norms that do not translate well to cities like Bristol [53, 54]. Prior research has demonstrated that in-context information can lead to biased label predictions, especially in models that rely heavily on contextual retrieval for inference [55–57]. This means that geographical and domain-specific retrieved examples can actively influence the sentiment labels produced by the model. Therefore, using a different corpus, expanded to be more geographically diverse, larger in size, and inclusive of varied domains like transport and public services,

TABLE 9 | Top-1 retrieved examples for some of the binary inputs, and predicted labels from Flan-T5-large using RAG.

Input	Retrieved example	Predicted
<i>Sentence:</i> Cars go really fast down my road as it is a rat rather great to see one way or traffic calming measures. <i>Label:</i> Negative	<i>Sentence:</i> Traffic is light after the evening rush hour and they move quite quickly LOCATION1 is alright just do not talk to any strangers, you know the standard things. <i>Label:</i> Positive	Positive
<i>Sentence:</i> Provide a regular bus service for St Annes/Brislington, Barton Hill to get into town. <i>Label:</i> Negative	<i>Sentence:</i> There is a 24-hour bus, the 176, which goes to Oxford St There are other buses which go to LOCATION1. <i>Label:</i> Positive	Positive
<i>Sentence:</i> The path along the river is lovely in the day but scary at night as there is no lighting and so is pitch black <i>Label:</i> Negative	<i>Sentence:</i> What scares me most is if this is LOCATION1 during the day heavens knows what it becomes of a night. <i>Label:</i> Positive	Negative
<i>Sentence:</i> Lovely natural space enjoyed by many, great views, lots of places to sit and enjoy. <i>Label:</i> Positive	<i>Sentence:</i> Lots of lovely scenery in LOCATION1 and LOCATION2. <i>Label:</i> Positive	Positive

as well as diverse demographic and cultural contexts, could lead to more accurate and generalizable results. Additionally, the retrieval metric used can also impact the outcomes [58]. The choice of similarity metric dictates how the system evaluates and ranks the relevance of documents from the knowledge base in response to a given query.

4.1.3 | Comparative Analysis: Zero-Shot and Fine-Tuned Approaches

Zero-shot LLMs offer notable advantages in terms of deployment speed, eliminating the need for large labeled datasets, and providing a conversational interface that requires minimal technical expertise. To explore their effectiveness in domain-specific sentiment classification, we have compared their performance against fine-tuned models. For this purpose, we have selected BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [59] as the baseline, given its consistent state-of-the-art results on sentiment analysis tasks [10, 60]. Unlike generative models, such as Flan-T5, that produce text autoregressively, BERT processes the entire input at once. This allows it to take into account context from both directions of the text, making it especially effective for

TABLE 10 | Performance Comparison of Flan-T5 Models with and without RAG Integration for 3-class classification.

Models	Metric	With RAG	Without RAG
Flan-T5-small	Accuracy	0.42	0.51
	F1-Score	0.47	0.56
Flan-T5-base	Accuracy	0.64	0.65
	F1-Score	0.66	0.68
Flan-T5-large	Accuracy	0.78	0.77
	F1-Score	0.79	0.78

TABLE 11 | Performance Comparison of Flan-T5 Models with and without RAG Integration for 5-class classification.

Models	Metric	With RAG	Without RAG
Flan-T5-small	Accuracy	0.29	0.38
	F1-Score	0.29	0.36
Flan-T5-base	Accuracy	0.37	0.30
	F1-Score	0.39	0.35
Flan-T5-large	Accuracy	0.25	0.23
	F1-Score	0.16	0.14

TABLE 12 | Accuracy comparison of sentiment classification methods on EBLN dataset under zero-shot and fine-tuned settings.

Model	Training domain	EBLN labels	2-classes	3-classes	5-classes
Flan-T5	—	—	[0.81 – 0.92]	[0.51 – 0.77]	[0.23 – 0.38]
Flan-T5 + RAG	SentiHood (knowledge base)	—	[0.88 – 0.95]	[0.42 – 0.78]	[0.25 – 0.37]
BERT fine-tuned	SentiHood (train set)	—	0.88	0.68	0.53
BERT fine-tuned	EBLN (train set)	10 samples (~ 2%)	0.88	0.78	0.54
		100 samples (~ 20%)	0.92	0.81	0.57

classification tasks where a comprehensive understanding of the complete sentence context is crucial.

We evaluated BERT under two training configurations representing different real-world data availability scenarios. First, BERT was fine-tuned on the SentiHood dataset to parallel our RAG experiments. While RAG uses SentiHood as an external knowledge base providing examples for augmented prompts, fine-tuning embeds this knowledge directly into the model's parameters. This configuration tests similar domain knowledge transfer when target domain labels are unavailable. Second, we fine-tuned BERT on limited EBLN samples (10 and 100 examples) to determine how many labeled samples are required for supervised methods to match or surpass zero-shot approaches. Table 12 presents accuracy across all configurations for 2-class, 3-class, and 5-class sentiment classification tasks. For Flan-T5, we report the range between minimum and maximum accuracy obtained across the three model sizes tested (small, base, and large).

The results of the fine-tuning indicate that supervised learning becomes increasingly beneficial as the complexity of the task rises. While zero-shot and fine-tuned approaches achieve comparable binary classification accuracy, fine-tuning significantly outperforms the lower bounds of zero-shot Flan-T5 in multi-class scenarios. As discussed earlier, zero-shot models depend on their pretrained understanding of sentiment, which effectively captures broad polarity (positive vs. negative) but lacks the detailed calibration necessary for more nuanced categories [33]. Fine-tuning, even with a small number of samples, enables the model to adjust its decision boundaries to align with the specific sentiment expression patterns of the target domain [60]. Remarkably, merely 10 labeled examples from the target dataset can yield high accuracy, making in-domain fine-tuning particularly practical. This approach is particularly appealing compared to fine-tuning on an external dataset like SentiHood, as it eliminates the dependency on sourcing large, domain-similar corpora. Fine-tuning on an external dataset remains a viable alternative when labeled data is unavailable, provided that the dataset is highly similar and sufficiently large. However, both strategies inherit the rigidity of supervised learning: any domain shift, such as new surveys or contexts, requires retraining with fresh labeled samples or external data. Additionally, these methods demand technical expertise in data preprocessing, model training, hyperparameter tuning, and infrastructure (e.g., GPU access), creating barriers for nontechnical teams. This contrasts with zero-shot approaches, where users simply provide natural language instructions without any machine learning expertise, and crucially, can adapt to new domains or survey topics instantly by modifying the prompt.

FIGURE 5 | Two human experts from the Bristol City Council evaluated 10 contexts for each model (Table 3).

When evaluating the performance-effort trade-off, the optimal approach depends critically on task complexity and deployment context. For binary sentiment classification, zero-shot methods provide the best performance-effort balance: they achieve competitive accuracy with no annotation costs, no technical expertise, and instant adaptability to new domains. For multiclass tasks, minimal in-domain fine-tuning provides better results, though not at the level of binary classification. In these cases, more nuanced strategies, such as advanced prompting or sentiment analysis on specific aspects, may yield further improvements.

4.2 | Text Summarization

For the summarization, we performed a domain expert evaluation. The results are shown in Figure 5. Previously, we demonstrated that LLaMA 3 exhibited superior performance when evaluated using naive system prompts [61]. In this study, we extend our analysis to include additional models, notably LLaMA 3.1, incorporating prompt engineering techniques. The expert evaluations indicate that LLaMA 3.1 outperforms all other evaluated models, establishing it as the most effective within the scope of our experiments. However, in some cases, the summaries contained content not relevant to the context (e.g., Contexts 2, 4, and 7), though, except for Context 2, the summaries were considered concise and useful overall. We hypothesize that this is likely due to the fact that the responses contain sparse content relevant to the context. We suggest that this merits further investigation.

It should be noted that traditional summarization techniques (LSA and LexRank), and Pegasus, produced summaries that lacked coherence and narrative flow. This limitation is likely attributable to the nature of the survey responses, which frequently consisted of incomplete phrases and fragmented terms. In contrast, more sophisticated models, particularly LLMs, demonstrated significantly better performance when handling such input.

Consequently, LSA, LexRank, and Pegasus were excluded from the evaluation. Furthermore, BART-CNN-Large, which does not accept prompts, generated only a single summary. It contained more information as compared to the other traditional approaches, but still lacked coherence and flow, and was given a score of 1 (low) by both reviewers. For the sake of conciseness, this result is omitted from Figure 5.

It is also important to note that, for the purposes of this study, the survey responses were sufficiently concise to fit within the context window of the evaluated models. However, as the number of responses increases, this may lead to the issue of *context rot* in LLMs, wherein the model's ability to retain and utilize earlier information degrades [62]. In such cases, it may be necessary to implement the chunking strategy to manage input length and preserve summarization quality when using LLMs as well.

5 | Conclusion

In this paper, we argued that GenAI, more specifically LLMs, can be used for data analysis by public authorities. In particular, we investigated sentiment analysis and summarization using open-source LLM and applied them to survey data from the EBLN case study. The results show that larger versions of LLMs consistently improve accuracy in binary sentiment classification tasks. As model size increased, performance metrics showed steady improvements, indicating better capture of nuanced patterns. However, this came with longer execution times, although it remained more efficient than manual analysis. By contrast, increasing the number of sentiment categories does not necessarily lead to better results. This can be attributed to the fact that LLMs often struggle with more complex tasks and finer-grained distinctions, which can introduce additional challenges and reduce overall accuracy.

Our findings suggest that incorporating RAG further enhances the performance of LLMs for sentiment classification. The

integration of external knowledge bases through RAG allows the models to access a broader context, leading to more accurate and contextually relevant outputs. However, the effectiveness of RAG is influenced by the quality and relevance of the knowledge base and the retrieval approach used. To maximize the benefits of RAG, developing and maintaining comprehensive, context-specific datasets for use as a knowledge base could be highly beneficial.

Our investigation concluded that LLaMA 3.1 8B consistently produces useful, concise, and relevant summaries, though hallucinations likely remain a concern in situations where content is sparse. We suggest that further fine-tuning of the prompt could result in reducing such hallucinations.

We anticipate that such GenAI-based services can provide efficient means to public authorities in performing data analysis and evaluating or assessing public opinion. These systems can process diverse data sources, including social media, comments on planning applications, petitions, etc. However, further research is needed to improve the accuracy of sentiment classification and summarization of survey data. Our future work will focus on comparing LLMs with conventional models across these diverse data sources to understand their relative strengths and weaknesses. We plan to evaluate various LLMs for task-specific suitability, and explore prompt engineering techniques to optimize performance. For sentiment classification, we aim to implement aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) to understand more nuanced patterns and provide insights into both emotions and topics within the text. Regarding summarization tasks, we intend to incorporate RAG techniques to improve contextual relevance by implementing prefiltering of responses before inputting them to the LLM for summarization. Additionally, we will investigate how biases inherent in the training data of LLMs can impact the results and performance of the models, as understanding these biases helps in ensuring fair and accurate results.

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Disclosure

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The dataset used for the sentiment analysis component of this study was sourced from the EBLN project and is publicly available online (<https://eastbristolliveableneighbourhoods.commonplace.is/map/map>). The data used for the summarization task was kindly provided by Bristol City Council. Both datasets were used in accordance with their respective licensing and ethical guidelines.

Endnotes

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